

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10900183>

DEALING WITH DISRUPTIVE STUDENTS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to determine the causes of disruptive behavior among the first grade pupils. In order to facilitate the effective learning, it is important to clarify misbehaving in the classroom and avoid it.

Conducting research related to this topic, alongside gathering knowledge from other surveys, demonstrates that disruptive behavior may occur when classroom is not arranged properly. The aim of quantitative method in this investigation is to identify the forms and reasons of disruptive behavior among pupils by giving their appropriate percentage. In order to conduct the research one school where located in Navai had been chosen. About 30 pupils who are at the first grade had been interviewed and their teachers were asked to help find the occurrence of disruptive behavior among young learners.

Learning process is difficult one. It is commonly argued that if the classroom has a good atmosphere and support of teachers, students tend to learn effectively. Because the existence of disruptive behavior also depends on teachers' skills. When the teacher gives profitable knowledge to pupils, they desire to study a lot without any disruption.

Key words: *Disruption, quantitative method, disruptive behavior, punishment, bullying.*

INTRODUCTION

Students' behavior changes according to the level of education. Some students who are at the first grade may come across certain difficulties when they go to school at first. In this case, adaptation does not exist. This phenomenon becomes one of the most educational challenge about how to teach them effectively. It influences on the existence of students who have disruptive behavior. Students can be educated well if they desire to learn. Otherwise, they will not learn when they are not willing to study.

It is commonly believed that every classroom has its disruptive students. Firstly, what is “Disruption” itself?” “Disruption” as applied to the academic setting, means behavior that reasonable faculty member would view as interfering with normal academic functions. In short, disruption is misbehaviouring during the lesson. It can also be defined as behavior which disrupts or prevents instruction or learning activities. It is actually a difficult work to educate pupils with disruptive behavior.

Various management and discipline techniques are used by teachers in order to control students during the lesson and avoid disruption in the classroom. The pupils with disruptive character often present their disruptive actions such as backchat, laughing, ignoring the lesson, interrupting other classmates. While handling such students the teachers feel so stressful and unrewarding. Because they are mostly unaware of the reasons for these pupils’ character. The teachers who educate such classes must spend lots of time and energy to cope with pupils’ misbehavior. In this situation, they have to estimate the aspects of causing misbehavior like poor attitude, low IQ or limited study ability, the lack of parental support or physical problems, troubles with poor home environment (Muzaffar & Javaid, 2018). Such kind of perceptions on behalf of the educators indicate that they have very limited or no control over their students’ behavior. When a child goes to school at the first time, he or she may feel himself/herself uncomfortable. In order to adapt the school, pupil needs teachers’ support. Otherwise, student begins to get bored with the lesson and disrupt others. Because of being very young, students who are at the first grade may come across some learning difficulties on the first three months. If teachers do not help students to improve their character, such behavior may become long-lasting.

The influences of such misbehaviors in the classroom are regarded as very dangerous for other students.

There have been several researches related to students’ misbehaviouring. However, particular studies on the forms and sources of students’ disruptive behavior should be encouraged. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the first grade students’ behavior and find solutions to tackle it.

A range of studies was first reviewed and then a survey of 30 pupils was conducted to confirm disruptive behavior from them.

The paper has the following structure. The first section presents an analysis of the relevant research focusing on the current limited knowledge regarding the teachers’ experience. The second part shows the methodology of the survey and analysis of findings and the final section considers the implications of the results and some recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of researches and investigations have already been undertaken on students' disruptive behavior. Disruptive conduct refers to a set of inappropriate behaviors in pupils that prevent learning and interpersonal relations (McDaniel & Flower, 2015). In addition to this, Hulac and Benson (2010) mention that these behaviors of the students are usually characterized by the students' emotional nature. Disruptive behavior involves a certain amount of disobedience, confront and lack of respect means disrespect towards other fellows.

The literature illustrates the reasons of disruptive behavior during the class. Proshansky (1975) mentions that if classroom is not arranged properly disruptive behavior may exist.

Many types of disruptive behavior are found in a classroom, but in general, forms of disruptive behavior fall into one of three categories: Behavior by the student individually (including while interacting with technology), behavior interacting with other students, and behavior interacting with the instructor. Disruptions can be caused by a group of students together, such as carrying on conversations, passing notes between students, or cheating on an exam. This may lead to further disruptions and to the involvement of additional students.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is quantitative research using a questionnaire from teachers and pupils. Research is conducted in Elementary school in Navai and the target audience consists of both students and teachers. The population of study comprised the first grade elementary-level students and their teachers. There were 30 students and three teachers in the selected school.

The research data is in the form of information about factors that influence the disruptive behavior of students in the classroom. The data source comes from teachers and students. Data analysis used in the study uses an interactive model according to the level of students.

Quantitative research in education has roots in several academic disciplines including the social sciences and the humanities. Moreover, this research has been influenced by the postmodern approaches to inquiry (Gall, Gall & Borg, 2007).

This method has been used in many studies. Including the advantages of this research is that it is easier to find solutions to many educational problems with this method than others. During the research, an individual interview was conducted with over 30 1st grade students and they had been interviewed about the difficulty and preference of study at school, the level of lessons, whether the teachers' knowledge

and skills are satisfactory or not was carried out. Students participated in this research with their unbiased opinions. The questionnaire taken from the students was about coming to school for the first time, adapting to it, listening to the teachers during the whole lesson and other similar topics and the target audience actively participated in this questionnaire.

Since a quantitative approach is used in this research, it can be seen as useful to the first discuss the differences between qualitative and quantitative methods. This comparison can underscore the benefits of using a quantitative approach in addressing the research questions posed this study.

The questionnaire was also administered to the Elementary school teachers in order to gain their opinion regarding the factors of existence of disruptive behavior among the pupils.

The following are the list of students' disruptive behavior obtained from observation and the percentage of them that shows the existence of misbehavior. The perceived pupils are the first grade. The following is the complete list of questions in the questionnaire:

Rate these behaviors using the following 1-5 scale:

_____ I feel myself homesick when studying at school.

_____ I do not want to listen to my teachers.

_____ All textbooks are boring to me.

_____ I desire to play with other students during the lesson.

_____ I have difficulties to adapt the school and teachers.

_____ I want to whisper, cheat with my friends.

_____ I hate doing homework, because they are not needed.

_____ I want to walk around the classroom during the lesson.

Students were asked to rate those opinions according to their character. In addition to this, in this survey, their teachers were also interviewed in order to find the causes of disruptive behaviors among the students. The questionnaire which conducted among the teachers is following:

Write your Yes/No answer in these statements.

_____ Students misbehave themselves if we do not teach effectively.

_____ I really hate and do not want to teach students with disruptive behavior.

_____ My students have not disruptive behavior because I am the best teacher.

_____ Students do not know the rules of school.

_____ I always teach my students with shouting.

_____ I am very stressed and nervous teacher.

_____ I like working with disruptive pupils.

_____ I have no any practice to deal with disruptive students.

Certainly, this questionnaire holds significant role in enhancing the precision of the research and helps to solve problems related to dealing with disruptive students.

RESULT

It is obvious that controlling everything by the teacher during the lesson is more complex one. One of the most difficult aspects of teaching the first grade pupils is that students tend to gather and play with each other in the classroom. Obviously, in this case, the teacher gets stressed and does not educate them or wants to punish students with disruptive behavior.

The conducted research demonstrates that sometimes young pupils exhibit disruptive behaviors due to not yet fully adapting to school. This does not necessarily indicate a lack of systematic acceptance and disciplined behavior. In such cases, continuous programs and individualized plans and diagnoses are required. According to the research about 60 % of students feel themselves homesick when they go to school. The remaining results of the research are as follows:

From the table 1, some insights can be drawn. There 60 % of pupils who feel homesick during the lesson. Thirty one percent of students say that they do not want to listen to their teachers and are not ready for homework. Textbooks are boring and difficult for 51 % students. Over 47 % of pupils desire to play, whisper and cheat with others. Twenty six percent illustrates the difficulties of adapting to school. Eleven percent of pupils walk around the classroom.

According to the second diagram teachers believe whether they teach efficiently and attentionally, students tend to study hard. Moreover, one teacher admitted that she has no practice to deal with disciplined pupils and she usually gets stressed. Both teachers argue that most students do not know the disciplines of school.

CONCLUSION

In summary, it remains an important issue to educate disciplined students over the world. Many scientists mention that it is possible to avoid it. Moreover, it actually depends on teachers' skill. They should not punish students who are disruptive in the class. It is necessary for educators to understand disruptive pupils and take action accordingly to address the root causes of poor behavior. Because punishment is not the only solution. The findings demonstrate that the pupils interviewed said that they carry out some very negative acts during the lesson. They also gave a number of reasons why they had acted in this way, including homesickness, boredom, tiredness, hate of lesson and a response to bullying. However. It is reasonable that disruptive pupils want to be treated respectfully and learn more in their current contexts of study.

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